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EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF THE PROCESS-BASED APPROACH ON EFL STUDENTS’ ACADEMIC WRITING SKILLS

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Annotation. This study explores the effectiveness of a process-based writing approach in improving IELTS Writing Task 1 performance among B2-level secondary EFL learners. Five ninth-grade students completed a two-hour writing cycle that involved brainstorming, drafting, peer exchange, reconstructing graphs from peers’ texts, and revision. A comparison of the first and final drafts, along with learner reflections, revealed improvements in clarity, organization, and reporting accuracy. Students also demonstrated increased confidence and awareness of audience needs. Although limited in scale and duration, the experiment suggests that process-oriented instruction led to noticeable improvements in clarity, data reporting accuracy, and task organization in IELTS academic writing.

Keywords: process-based approach, IELTS Writing Task 1, EFL learners, academic writing, peer revision, drafting, learner reflection, secondary education.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot jarayonli (process-based) yondashuvining B2 darajadagi maktab o‘quvchilarining IELTS Writing Task 1 natijalariga ta’sirini o‘rganadi. Xususi o‘quv markazida besh nafar 9-sinf o‘quvchilari ikki soatlik yozuv mashg‘ulotida ishtirok etdi. Dars davomida ular brainstorming (g‘oyalar ishlab chiqarish), drafting (qoralama), peer exchange (tengdoshlar bilan almashish), matn asosida grafikni qayta tasvirlash va tahrir qilish bosqichlarini bajarishdi. Tadqiqot hajmi va davomiyligi cheklangan bo‘lishiga qaramay, tajriba jarayonli yondashuv asosidagi ta’lim IELTS akademik yozuvida fikrning aniqligi, ma’lumotlarni aniq ifodalash va topshiriq tuzilmasining yaxshilanishiga olib kelganini ko‘rsatdi.

Kalit so‘zlar: jarayonli yondashuv, IELTS Task 1, EFL, tahrirlash, qoralama, o‘quvchi refleksiya, maktab o‘quvchilari.

Аннотация. В данном исследовании рассматривается эффективность процессного подхода к обучению письму при подготовке к IELTS Writing Task 1 среди школьников уровня B2. Пять учащихся девятого класса участвовали в двухчасовом занятии, включающем brainstorming (генерировать идеи), drafting (написание черновика), обмен работами (peer exchange), восстановление графика по тексту одноклассника и последующее редактирование. Сравнение первоначальных и итоговых текстов, а также рефлексивные комментарии студентов показали улучшение в структуре, точности передачи данных и ясности изложения. Несмотря на ограниченный масштаб и продолжительность, эксперимент показал, что процессно-ориентированное обучение привело к заметным улучшениям в ясности изложения, точности передачи данных и организации задания в академическом письме IELTS.

Ключевые слова: процессный подход, IELTS Task 1, навыки письма EFL, редактирование, черновик, рефлексия учащихся, школьники.

INTRODUCTION. Academic writing continues to pose significant challenges for EFL learners (Benchiheb, Laiouer, Bouhali, 2022), particularly in contexts where students are preparing for academic exams such as IELTS. In recent years, approaches to writing instruction have shifted away from traditional classroom models toward methods that actively engage learners in the writing process. Process-based pedagogy, which emphasizes planning, drafting, revising, and editing, has become central to contemporary teaching practice and is widely recognized for developing learner autonomy, coherence, and accuracy (Samsudin, 2016). Collaborative strategies such as peer review and shared drafting have gained increasing attention, supported by sociocultural perspectives that view learning as a socially communicative activity. Even though process-based writing has been widely studied in higher education, its application in IELTS Task 1 instruction at the secondary school level remains underexplored.

This article situates these developments within the broader field of TESOL methodology and argues that combining process-based instruction, collaborative learning techniques, and carefully managed digital support can create a more effective pathway for developing academic writing skills. By examining theoretical perspectives and classroom applications, the discussion aims to demonstrate how these approaches can better equip learners to interpret visual data, structure ideas, and produce polished writing suitable for academic and test-oriented contexts.

LITERATURE REVIEW. Research on academic writing instruction has increasingly shifted from traditional product-oriented approaches toward process-based pedagogies that foreground writing as a recursive, socially mediated activity. Early process theorists such as Leki (1998) emphasized that writing is not simply the production of a final text but a series of cognitive and social processes that involve planning, drafting, revising, and editing. This approach contrasts with traditional models that focus primarily on the final product and teacher correction (Leki, 1998).

Process-based instruction has been shown to enhance learners’ metacognitive awareness and autonomy. Heffernan (2006) argued that integrating stages of planning, drafting, and revision encourages students to reflect on their choices and become active agents in their own development. Hyland (2016) further highlighted that process writing allows learners to experiment with language in a low-stakes environment, facilitating increased accuracy and complexity over time. In this view, repeated drafting and peer collaboration help learners to internalize linguistic structures and rhetorical patterns.

Collaborative activities, such as peer review/assessment and shared drafting, are also integral to contemporary process writing pedagogy. Sociocultural perspectives on second and foreign language learning suggest that interaction with peers and more competent others mediates development (Vygotsky, as cited in Hyland, 2016). Studies have shown that peer interaction not only helps learners identify gaps in content and organization but also reinforces awareness of audience needs. For example, in process-oriented classrooms, students engage in the exchange of drafts and negotiation of meaning, which promotes deeper engagement with task requirements (Samsudin, 2016). This aligns with research by Widodo (2008), who found that process-based academic writing instruction in EFL contexts improves not only linguistic accuracy but also task fulfillment and logical structuring.

While much of the literature focuses on tertiary education, there is also an emerging interest in applying process approaches to secondary and exam-oriented contexts. Berdiyeva (2024) discussed the need for innovative teaching strategies in EFL classrooms that move beyond rote memorization to activities that develop analytical and expressive skills. Similarly, research on the methodological difficulties faced by EFL learners during dissertation writing highlights the limitations of product-only approaches, which do not support the recursive refinement of ideas (Benchiheb, Laiouer, Bouhali, 2022). These studies underscore the importance of instruction that supports learners through planning and revision, particularly when the writing task involves the interpretation of data or complex input.

In the specific context of IELTS preparation, the process approach has been less extensively researched, especially at the secondary school level. Samsudin’s (2016) comparison of process and product approaches in academic writing instruction revealed that students taught through process-oriented methods demonstrated greater improvement in coherence and cohesion than those taught through traditional product pedagogy. Although this study was conducted with undergraduates, its findings suggest that secondary learners may similarly benefit from recursive writing practice.

Despite this, there remains a gap in the literature regarding the application of process writing in IELTS Writing Task 1, which requires a concise and accurate description of visual data. This gap is notable because Task 1 demands both linguistic precision and task achievement, making it a suitable arena to evaluate the impact of process pedagogy. The current study aims to address this gap by exploring how process-based instruction, supported by peer collaboration and iterative

revision, influences learners’ clarity, organizational skills, and confidence in producing Task 1 reports.

METHODOLOGY. This study employed a small-scale classroom experiment to investigate the effectiveness of the process-based approach in teaching IELTS Academic Writing Task 1. The study adopted a qualitative classroom-based action research design aimed at examining the impact of process-oriented writing instruction on learners’ performance in IELTS Task 1. The research was conducted in a private learning center with a group of five 9th-grade EFL learners (aged 14-15) preparing for the IELTS examination. The students’ proficiency level was assessed as B2+ according to CEFR descriptors. The session lasted two hours and was integrated into their regular writing instruction schedule.

The procedure followed the key stages of the writing process: prewriting, drafting, revising, and editing. At the beginning of the lesson, each participant was assigned a different IELTS Task 1 chart or graph. Learners first engaged in individual brainstorming to identify key data, overall trends, and comparative features. They then produced a first draft within a 20-minute time limit. To reinforce meaning comprehension and structural clarity, students exchanged drafts and attempted to reconstruct the original visual data solely from the writing produced by a peer. This activity aimed to reveal gaps in description, missing details, or unclear language.

Following the reconstruction task, learners returned to their own drafts, reviewed peer comments, and edited their reports for accuracy, coherence, and vocabulary. Finally, revised essays were submitted for teacher assessment. Data were collected through comparison of first and final drafts, written self-reflections, and teacher observations. The combination of structured writing stages, peer interaction, and reflective revision provided insight into how the process approach influences learners’ clarity, accuracy, and confidence when producing academic texts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The findings of the classroom experiment indicate that the process-based approach had a positive effect on learners’ clarity, structure, and overall confidence in completing IELTS Writing Task 1. Drafts and final essays were analyzed not only with the help of the band descriptor of the IELTS writing task 1, but also in relation to learners’ self-reported confidence during the writing process. A comparison of first and final drafts revealed noticeable improvement in sentence accuracy, organization of ideas, and ability to summarize key data. For example, student A’s first draft was very general, and trends were mentioned vaguely; in the final draft, however, the trend and details were stated clearly and well-supported. In all five students’ work, revisions included clearer reporting verbs, more precise vocabulary, and better paragraphing, suggesting that guided rewriting supported language development.

One of the most significant gains emerged from the reconstruction activity. When students attempted to recreate visual data using only a peer’s text, they immediately recognized gaps in detail, missing figures, and ambiguous sequencing. This experience heightened their awareness of reader needs and encouraged them to

add clearer comparisons, numerical details, and overall trends in later drafts. The activity reinforced an important principle of academic writing: writing must not simply record information; it must communicate it to a reader unfamiliar with the source. Learner reflections also demonstrated increased autonomy and engagement. Students reported that drafting and revising made the task “less stressful” and helped them “notice what needs to change”, resulting in reduced task-related anxiety in essay writing. This aligns with previous research arguing that process-oriented writing builds metacognitive awareness, encourages independent problem solving, and reduces reliance on teacher correction (Hyland, 2016).

However, the experiment also highlighted challenges. Some learners expressed uncertainty during drafting, feeling unsure whether ideas were “correct” without immediate teacher validation. This suggests that EFL learners may require more scaffolding to feel confident generating text without model answers. Additionally, the small sample size and short instructional duration limit the generalizability of findings.

Overall, the results suggest that the process approach, supported by peer feedback and reflective revision, can enhance learner performance on IELTS Task 1. Students not only produced more accurate writing but also demonstrated greater control over language and content. The combination of repeated drafting, peer interaction, and guided editing appears to foster transferable skills that strengthen long-term writing development rather than one-time task completion. These improvements highlight the effectiveness of process-oriented instructions, which were argued by Leki, who emphasized that repeated writing drafts enhance clarity and the writer’s awareness.

CONCLUSION. This classroom-based experiment demonstrated that the process approach to teaching IELTS Writing Task 1 can effectively support secondary-level EFL learners in developing stronger academic writing skills. By guiding students through brainstorming, drafting, peer exchange, and revision, the intervention moved students beyond a product-only orientation. It encouraged them to view writing as a recursive and reflective process. The comparison between initial and revised drafts showed improvement in organization, clarity, and use of task-appropriate language, suggesting that process-oriented instruction can enhance both linguistic accuracy and rhetorical control.

The activity requiring students to reconstruct graphs from peers’ drafts proved particularly impactful. It helped learners recognize missing or unclear information, develop audience awareness, and revise more deliberately. Student reflections further confirmed that repeated drafting increased confidence and reduced anxiety associated with writing tasks. Despite promising results, the study was limited by its small sample size and short timeframe. Future research involving larger groups and extended teaching cycles would enable a more comprehensive evaluation of the approach. Nevertheless, the experiment provides preliminary evidence that the process-based method offers a meaningful pathway for improving IELTS writing performance in EFL contexts and may be especially valuable when combined with peer collaboration and guided practice.

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NEFT VA GAZ TERMINOLOGIYASIDA DISKURSIV VA PRAGMATIK OMILLAR

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur ilmiy maqolada neft va gaz terminologiyasining shakllanishi, rivojlanishi va amaliy qo‘llanishida diskursiv hamda pragmatik omillarning o‘rni kompleks tarzda tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot terminlarni faqat nominativ birlik sifatida emas, balki muayyan professional, institutsional va kommunikativ diskurs doirasida faoliyat yurituvchi til birliklari sifatida talqin qiladi. Neft va gaz sohasi global miqyosda strategik ahamiyatga ega bo‘lgani sababli, unda qo‘llaniladigan terminologiya ko‘p tillilik, madaniyatlararo muloqot va institutsional normalalar bilan chambarchas bog‘liqdir. Maqolada ingliz, rus va o‘zbek tillaridagi neft va gaz terminlari misolida diskursiv kontekst, pragmatik maqsad, adresant–adresat munosabati hamda tarjima jarayonidagi moslashuv muammolari yoritiladi. Tadqiqot natijalari terminologiya nazariyasi, kasbiy diskurs tahlili va maxsus soha tarjimasini uchun ilmiy-amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi.